

Yielding to a higher power

Luke 7:1 – 10

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Luke 7:1 When He had completed all His discourse in the hearing of the people, He went to Capernaum. **2** And a centurion's slave, who was highly regarded by him, was sick and about to die. **3** When he heard about Jesus, he sent some Jewish elders asking Him to come and save the life of his slave. **4** When they came to Jesus, they earnestly implored Him, saying, "He is worthy for You to grant this to him; **5** for he loves our nation and it was he who built us our synagogue." **6** Now Jesus *started* on His way with them; and when He was not far from the house, the centurion sent friends, saying to Him, "Lord, do not trouble Yourself further, for I am not worthy for You to come under my roof; **7** for this reason I did not even consider myself worthy to come to You, but *just* say the word, and my servant will be healed. **8** "For I also am a man placed under authority, with soldiers under me; and I say to this one, 'Go!' and he goes, and to another, 'Come!' and he comes, and to my slave, 'Do this!' and he does it." **9** Now when Jesus heard this, He marveled at him, and turned and said to the crowd that was following Him, "I say to you, not even in Israel have I found such great faith." **10** When those who had been sent returned to the house, they found the slave in good health.

In Luke chapter 7 verses 1 to 10, we have the story of a centurion slave who became very ill, and the centurion came to Jesus in order to save him. One of the interesting things I want to bring out in this narrative is that if you take it from the Greek and bring it back to the original language of Jesus, which is Aramaic, the centurion becomes a soldier of Herod Antipas, who was the king of the Galilee. When you do that, this soldier could have been Jewish immediately comes to mind. Therefore, this narrative can apply to all people, Gentiles and Jews alike.

The soldier clarified he had the authority over his men. He could tell them what to do and they would have to do it no matter what. This put him in a position of authority. Whether the soldier was working for Rome or for Herod, the soldier had the authority

to also, shall we say, bully the average person? Perhaps bullying is too rough of a word. Let's say this person was a peacemaker. It would be like a police force today. Their primary aim is to maintain the peace of the communities that they are protecting.

This soldier could've enlightened and demanded, or even ordered him, to cure his servant. However, he did not do that. He humbled himself before Jesus and basically said to him, Jesus have authority over me, and I need your help. He asked him to please help him because he knew in his heart that he was standing before God's Messiah. If we think of this soldier as being Jewish, then we can say that he understood God's true purpose for the Messiah.

But what do I mean by that? Let me give you a little of the history of the Messiah tradition at the time of Jesus' life. The Romans had overseen the Galilee and Judea since around 68 BCE. So, they have been around for well over 100 years. The Romans oppressed the people in their empire, especially in the Near East. To top that off in Jesus' day, we had the remnants of Herod the Great's kingdom. Herod Antipas, who was a son of Herod, oversaw the area which Jesus lived in. Herod Antipas lived in luxury and in beauty, while his subjects lived in poverty. He oppressed the people by collecting additional taxes on top of the Roman taxes because he wanted to support his life of luxury. People had very little hope except they knew God was sending his Messiah. The people knew God would send his Messiah, who would be a son of David, and would liberate Israel from the oppressors, restore the nation, and give them hope amid their struggles.

History tells us that during the reign of David and Solomon, Israel was prosperous and strong. When the kingdom divided into two after Solomon's death, the two nations alone could not stop all the surrounding nations from exploiting them. The Maccabees led the restoration of the nation of Judah for about 100 years. However, the Maccabees were constantly fighting with the Syrians and eventually, in 68 BCE; they asked the Romans to help them. The Romans came into the country and decided that they needed the land bridge that Judah represented between the north of their empire and the kingdom of Egypt, which they were about to conquer. Therefore, Judah came under the control of Rome. And for 100 years, the people prayed to God for the Messiah.

This passage about the centurion whose servant became ill and came to Jesus tells us he got the messianic tradition right. The Messiah was first going to come and restore the spirituality of the people and their faith in God. The second coming of the Messiah was to be the war against the oppressors. We can find this idea in the book of Zechariah in the ninth chapter, the ninth verse. If we read further into Rabbinic literature, we find that the idea of the Messiah coming twice was a part of the faith of the people. Since it was a relatively new idea, it was not a powerful idea.

The mystical books talk about the Messiah ben Joseph and the Messiah ben David. The word *ben* in Hebrew means son of. So, the first Messiah, Jesus ben Joseph, was to come and restore the spiritual awareness and faith in God. After a period of time, you can find this in the book of the Revelation, God would send Messiah ben David, who would be the elite warrior. If you want to learn more about the second coming of the Messiah, then you need to read the Revelation. You can also find this idea in the book of Daniel, Isaiah, and several of the minor prophets.

Now I've given you all that background. What are we supposed to do with this passage in our daily lives? No matter who we are, there's always someone who is going to be in authority over us. In our daily lives, we are going to have to live by the rules and laws of our society and our country. If you don't follow the local laws, you could end up in jail. This applies at the state level and at the federal level. Therefore, we have no choice but to follow these laws if we want to maintain our freedom.

If you are working, which probably most of us are, we have a boss that we report to. Even people that have their own business in a way report to their customers. Because if their customers are not happy with what they are receiving, the business will eventually fizzle out. So, in this narrative, Jesus comes in and says, "Sure, you do not have to obey those people. Remember who the ultimate authority is over you and your life."

Jesus Christ is the ultimate authority because he is God, therefore God is your ultimate authority. Therefore, if you want to know if you're going in the right direction in your life and making decisions that please God, then you have to ask. That's what a good portion of prayer is about. Ask Jesus if the direction you're going in is right. He will never let you down. You may not get the answer you want, and it may take more time than you expect, but remember to wait for that answer.

Let me leave you with an example from the Hebrew Scriptures. The Israelites under King Saul were preparing for war against the Philistines. The prophet Samuel said to the king that he needed to wait until the prophet showed up because he was going to pray to God to find out what should be done. King Saul got overly anxious and started

the battle without Samuel. Samuel showed up during the battle as the Philistines beat the Israelites and took the Ark of the Covenant with them as a prize of war. Samuel looked at Saul and said you did not wait for me, therefore you did not wait for God, therefore you decided you were the ultimate authority and you're not. At that point, Samuel said to Saul that God would remove him from the throne and that his family would never be kings of Israel.

Remember that Jesus is our ultimate authority. If you are trying to decide about a situation, I suggest you pray upon it but also look into the Gospels and see if you have an answer from God in the Gospels and I should expand that and say anywhere in the whole Bible. It isn't hard to find answers to your questions and prayers in the Bible because you can always use the Internet and search for an answer. May God bless you, especially when you allow him to lead your life.